

Emotions And Digital Photo Sharing In A Networked Smart Home

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Abstract

Experiences and emotional responses to the designed world are dynamic. They occur in time and space, through the flow of people's actions as they engage in activities [4]. Photographs are a very affective and efficient way of connecting people to each other. The activity of sharing photographs provides a support for people to communicate and share emotions [8]. Much has been done already in relation to digital photographs on the computer. Most of this work has focussed on the organisation, search and retrieval of libraries of digital photos, such as the PhotoFinder project by Shneiderman et al [5, 6]. What we will be looking at is preserving the emotions associated with pictures and making photo sharing a fun and more enjoyable experience for the user.

Preliminary findings from our survey to measure attitudes towards digital photo sharing have revealed that most people believe that photos are representations of life's timeline, which bring out our emotions when we view them. The survey has revealed that people find photos to be intimate and representation of ones social lifestyle. We will be looking at how people relate themselves to pictures and if we could capture their emotions and expressions to store them in a way that is representative of their feelings towards the picture. As emotions can be associated with pictures of family, friends, places, holidays, social gatherings or travel to mention some of the aspects, we will also be looking at how emotions change over a period of time and how these emotions aid the user in decision making. This will allow us to look into the factors, which can make digital photo sharing fun and enjoyable. This can be achieved by capturing the facial expression of the users when he sees a particular picture, by allowing the user to write a message on the picture as he/she is viewing it on the central device or on a display medium, by allowing the user to attach sounds or record conversation regarding the picture. This will allow the user to elaborate the memories associated with photographs. This paper introduces the design guidelines for a generic home information system, which will allow us to receive, store and distribute digital information that is coming into the networked smart home. The project will look at digital photos and how can we attach emotions to pictures.

Introduction

Over the last few decades we have seen a massive increase not only in the power of microprocessors but also in some other technological parameters such as storage capacity and communication bandwidth [1]. This technological evolution has allowed the PC to become a personal communication tool and is being used in a variety of roles from spreadsheets, word processors, internet browsing, online shopping, photo sharing to email clients, instant messengers etc. Digital photography in combination with the Internet has enabled people to share photos with friends and families who are geographically separated. Despite these successes, web-based photo albums have yet to match the experience of sitting down with someone and sharing a stack of photos [2]. As our survey revealed that photos serve as memory triggers, which allow emotions and memories to be conjured up by the picture, hence we are trying to design a photo sharing software, which will allow users to preserve the emotions in digital photos. Photo uploading is often tedious, and there is no easy way of attaching voice or text annotations to the photos. One cannot highlight the relative importance of one photo against another, nor can one point out specific elements of a single photo [2].

Photography can be an expressive communication medium and because the crafting of emotion in your images makes a much more effective, more communicative image than one that is merely ambivalent. If we think back to the images that have moved us, it is their emotive qualities that got our attention [2]. Photo sharing is more persuasive if it's done in a face-to-face environment and we will be trying to reproduce the environment with our prototype. When you regroup and each person presents his or her images, it can be interesting to observe what people associate visually with each idea.

We should also mention the tremendous success of print clubs (pronounced "puricura"), which are located on every street corner in Japan. These machines are used by high school students to take their own photographs, later decorated with cute drawings and printed on small stickers. These stickers are then exchanged among friends and organized in large collections. What is interesting about print clubs is that they are computing devices that stress the social function of photographs. The various "socialware" products tremendously popular in Japan are a good illustration that entertainment and fun will also be affected by the emerging ubiquitous computing environment [9].

Emotions are mental states that arise spontaneously, rather than through conscious effort. Emotions are physical expressions, often involuntary, related to feelings, perceptions or beliefs about elements, objects or relations between them, in reality or in the imagination [1]. One problem with existing technologies is that they often require too much time and effort and are not designed to support lightweight, spontaneous interactions [8], which might occur while sharing photos. By making photo sharing less demanding and more engaging for the user, we can provide better support for people to people interactions. Emotions are very volatile and can be easily dispersed by a badly designed user interface. Emotions are also highly personal and subjective, which makes it difficult to test in a controlled fashion as they vary widely from one individual to another.

We feel that the three most important things to look at when designing products for a smart home are Functionality, Simplicity, and Aesthetics. The product should be able to carry out the tasks that the user wants. It should be simple to use and appealing enough to go with the decor of the home. When we design products for smart homes we should look at the quality of experience that people will have with that product and how it will be enjoyable. It is critical that designers strive to understand as much as possible about personal, social and cultural influences and interpretation of design elements and their expressions [4]. Only then we will be able to design quality products that will support people's experiences in an intended and pleasing way. The design should allow for prompting automatic reactive behavior from the user to carry out the task. The technological details of any product design should be hidden from the user, so that they can concentrate more on the task at hand. We need to know for example, not just whether people prefer a central device which can handle digital data distribution around their home, but also what attributes of the device will ensure that they keep enjoying the experience everytime they use it and want to identify with it.

Methodology

The project initially involved carrying out a survey regarding the concept of the data distribution device and how it will help with photo sharing in a smart home. The questionnaire helped in measuring attitudes towards the proposed features of the HIS, and its future developments. The feedback from the survey allowed us to use a top down approach to the system. This will allow us to start with a top-level description of a system and then refine this view step by step. With each refinement, the system will be decomposed into lower-level

and smaller modules. The major higher-level system requirements and functions will be identified, and will be broken down in successive steps until function-specific modules can be designed. The prototyping will help in collecting feedback from the users who have used the system and will be an iterative process where the system can be improved after every feedback from users.

Compared to work environments, where there is an almost embarrassing choice of methods of study, how and in what ways domestic environments may be best investigated for the purpose of design is largely an unknown quantity [13]. The nature of the home and the character of everyday home life are undergoing constant change in definition and as such are required to become responsive to the changing needs of people throughout their lifetime. This project will seek to simulate the home environment in a laboratory setting, using prototypes based on current high-end computing devices and other technologies. It will then assess the viability of the systems under conditions that equate to everyday use. In addition to experimental collection of data, attitudes to home technology and motivation towards its use will be measured using custom survey tools and a limited-ethnographic approach. The project will combine the technical aspects of home information system design with the cognitive ergonomics of devices aimed at the home market.

Our methodology is based on involving the users in the design process; hence we carried out this survey to gather preliminary information regarding interaction between people and their photos and what developments they would like to see in photo sharing. We want to see the social interaction people have with their photographs and what role photos play in our lives. The focus of this research is on human emotions, its relationship with pictures and how people would like to attach them to pictures, which will allow them to express their feelings towards a particular picture. We will also look at making photo sharing in the home as ubiquitous as possible by hiding the technological details from the user.

Results

To help us design photo-sharing software, we needed to get some idea as to what people like to do with photos and how they relate themselves to it. We carried out a survey to measure the attitude of people towards photo sharing. We looked at how people use photographs and how we can make photo sharing easy and fun. The survey dealt with questions regarding the usage

or cameras, the living environment, preference for digital or paper storage, medium for photo sharing, significance of a picture, emotional attachment, intimacy, indexing, usage of internet, reception, storage, and distribution. The survey allowed us to carry out a longitudinal study of changes in our emotions regarding pictures which will help us understand how people interact with photos and as to how they would like to capture these emotions associated with the pictures. The survey was distributed around the university via e-mail. We had 15 responses ranging from people with families, people living alone, and students living in student accommodation. There were 8 female respondents and 7 male respondents. Figure 1 shows the categorisation of respondents according to their age groups.

Figure 1. Number of respondents according to age group.

The first thing we looked at is the preference of respondents in storing their photographs. Figure 2 shows that a majority of people found the digital format more attractive than paper format for storing photographs.

Figure 2. Format people like to store photos in.

One respondent commented “I have old pictures in paper format, but I store new photos digitally”.

However the problem we face is the fact that there is still a vast majority of photos, which are in paper format. In coming years, if we do move to a completely digital format, these paper-based photos will need to be converted. At the moment there is no easy solution to this problem apart from scanning each photo individually and saving them in digital format.

Previous research [11] has brought this problem to light and has come up with the term “Funnel Effect”. It describes a funnel effect in digital photo taking, sharing, and printing. It means that people took many pictures, keep some of them, shared a selected group of those, and printed and even smaller subset. It might predict the trend for the future where people might just not bother with paper format. But at this moment this is just conjecture. Research at Berkeley [11] proposed that digital imaging is a key factor for many in the large volume of “throwaway” pictures, since, unlike regular photos, the cost of throwing away each digital photo is zero.

Next we looked at the social aspect of photo sharing. Figure 3 shows that most people like to share photos in a sociable environment. Photos are about people and their stories [3]. People tend to tell different stories, highlighting different aspects of the photos in different environments (Friends/Family). The contents of photos could illustrate the relationship between people. Photos are often given as gifts, which reinforces social connections. Nancy Et al [10] points out that sending photos to distant others is a way of keeping up on one another’s lives and telling stories about photos helps in nurturing relationships.

Figure 3. Photo sharing in a sociable environment.

One of the most important aspects of this survey was to find out if digital photography has made photo sharing easier. Figure 4 shows the result from the survey. With the advent of Internet and it becoming a part of more and more people’s lives, sharing photos with friends and families has become easier.

Figure 4. Has digital photography made photo sharing easier.

However we also wanted to see if sharing photos on display mediums (TV, Projection system, Digital Frames) would make photo sharing more fun and enjoyable. Figure 5 shows that most people think that sharing photos on a display medium is a much-preferred option.

Figure 5. Sharing digital photos on display mediums makes photo sharing more fun and enjoyable.

Some of those who preferred a display medium commented that viewing photos on a display medium allows more people to view the pictures rather than coming together in a confined viewing space. Display mediums also allow zooming into the pictures to get more details from the photo. People also find it cheaper, convenient, and viewing on display mediums makes it easier to put photos into different environments.

In terms of photos being a representation of life’s timeline, the response was very impressive as all the respondents accepted that photos are a representation of life’s timeline. A respondent commented, “I think your photos are your most valuable assets, many other things are replaceable”.

The response for the emotional attachment with pictures was interesting as respondents thought that viewing pictures brings out emotions in them. We also asked the subjects if they would like digital photos to represent personal emotions when viewing them (Figure 6). It was interesting to note that even the respondents who favoured using paper format for photo sharing wanted photos to be able to represent some form of emotion which could be in text format.

Figure 6. Respondents who would like digital photos to represent personal emotions.

Nancy et al [10] has suggested that the major use of photos is as a record reminder of individual and collective experiences, and to share experiences with others, such as using a family photo to give children a sense of family history. These uses are often heavily loaded with emotional significances.

We as human beings are social creatures who like to establish relationships. One of the most important ingredients of any relationship is the intimacy or the feeling we have towards other people. Photographs capture intimacy more as shared moments of closeness among the people in the picture and the person who is viewing them and may eventually help in building social relationships. It allows people to identify many different aspects of a person and could help in determining how people respond in different situations, because of the experiences you have had with them. What was fascinating about the relationship between photographs and intimacy is that a majority of respondents found photos to be intimate (Figure 7). Most respondents also found photos a representation of one's social lifestyle (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Photographs and intimacy.

Figure 8. Pictures are a representation of one's social lifestyle?

We wanted to know if emotions associated with a particular photo change over a period of time. Majority of respondents thought that emotions did change over a period of time (Figure 9). This may become one of the dimensions on which importance is endorsed to a particular picture, but that will not be part of this research.

Figure 9. Do emotions related to a picture change over a period of time?

We found that adding audio to photos will help in elaborating memories associated with photographs (Figure 10). Those who liked the idea of adding audio to digital photos commented:

“Sound could provide for strong memories so I might not want to attach a single sound”

“Overall, having a variety of sounds associated with the time would be most appropriate”

Figure 10. Addition of audio will help elaborate memories associated with pictures.

Another option people liked was the idea of adding text to a particular picture. One respondent explained that if a picture contains a group of people then the user could click on any part of the picture or the individual in that picture, which would open a dialogue box where the user can write a short description about that person or add a short audio description.

We wanted to know what people thought was the most important factor when sharing photos. As shown in Figure 11 most respondents thought involvement with the pictures of some sort was the most important aspect. However all the respondents selected the “Ease of use” option as well which meant that the survey result for this question were divided into two parts.

Figure 11. Important aspects with sharing photos.

People found that Reception and distribution of digital photos was sometimes restricted by lack of communication between different devices (Figure 12). However all the respondents

were very positive about having a central device in the home which could handle the reception, storage, and distribution of photos.

Figure 12. Photo sharing restricted by the lack of communication between different devices.

The results from the survey were very positive and have allowed us to come up with a proposed design scenario for a home information system, which will allow photo sharing within the home and allow the user to attach emotions to pictures. The second part of the survey involved questions, which required descriptive answers. The questions asked: -

1. How can digital technology support the intimacy normally found in photo sharing?
2. What aspect of a photograph will help in reviving the emotions (intimacy) associated with the particular memory?
3. What aspect of naming the pictures can be improved?
4. What single development will increase your usage of photos and photography and make photo sharing more fun and enjoyable?
5. Is randomisation and duplication of photo's (photo's stored on paper, pc, camera's etc) a problem?

The answers from the questions above helped us focus on some of the important aspects of photo sharing and its relationship with emotions. The results from the descriptive questions have been summarized later in this paper.

Proposed Design

With the advent of digital photography there seems to be endless stream of pictures that we want to share with our friends and loved ones. Digital images have allowed us to capture our emotions and build a kind of time travel machine that we can look at. What we will be looking at initially is how digital photos can be imported into the home, stored by the user, and then distributed across different viewable platforms in the home. The research will also look at exploring ways in which we can represent the emotional factors related with pictures

and how we can share it with our friends and family. We will be looking at using voice input and voice-to-text technology to represent emotions and also get user feedback as to how emotions change over a period of time. We will also be testing hand written messages over digital pictures, which will give them a personal feel when sharing with friends and families over the Internet. The figure below illustrates how digital photos can be imported from various devices into the central server. It is proposed that there will be various communication mediums available (USB, Bluetooth, IR, Wi-Fi etc), which will allow these devices to communicate with the central storage. Once the user has decided which photos they want, the images will be stored in the central storage system. The user can then view them on the handheld device or on a TV or a projection system as a slide show.

Figure 13. Home usage scenario

The product should be able to deliver the fun and creativity that comes from taking and sharing well-taken images [3]. Figure 13 shows the proposed interaction scenario for the home.

Looking at the aspects of entertainment within the home, there are several consumer electronics that provide multiple interaction mediums to communicate with each other. They

include devices like PC's, Notebooks, PDA's, TV's, Projectors, DVD, and Cameras etc. This multiple interaction medium could confuse the user and put them off using technology. What is needed is convergence of these technologies and interaction mediums, which could be achieved by providing an In-Home Communication Infrastructure, which can interact with all these devices and provide the comfort and convenience that the user expects. High-speed Internet connections are becoming a reality for home users now. We will be evaluating how these systems can be used to seamlessly connect dispersed families and friends through photo sharing.

We hope that in the future digital cameras will be equipped with some form of wireless connection, which will allow us to send the picture directly from the camera to the central server or view them on the handheld device. It will also allow photos to be displayed on display mediums directly from the camera as long as they are connected by a network connection. This might allow us to even capture the emotions of the viewer without their intervention. An example of this would be like having a camera installed in a display medium, which could capture the facial expression or audible emotions. Another option would be cameras with a built in GPS receiver in the camera, which would allow the photo to store the location as the picture is taken. Marc Et al [12] have developed a device called the MMM2 (Mobile Metadata for Media Sharing), which records spatial context (through CellID, Bluetooth-enabled GPS devices, and a fixed location Bluetooth objects such as PCs).

Summarization of Survey

The descriptive part of the questionnaire allowed respondents to describe some aspects concerning digital photography and how photo sharing can be improved. Advances in graphics and Internet have revolutionized the viewing and sharing of pictures. Pictures can be distributed through the Internet and viewed, however those pictures are a very basic representation of the message the photo is trying to convey. The intimacy, representation of one's social lifestyle and the personal emotions associated with the picture are hidden from the viewer at the other end of the network. Nancy et al [10] has identified a set of social uses of personal photography. They are constructing and maintaining social relationships, constructing personal and group memory, self-presentation, and self-expression.

Regarding the emotional aspects of pictures, respondents have suggested that allowing a brief description of the folders about how, when or on what specific occasion the pictures were taken, would help in reviving emotions associated with that particular photo or event. Photos should act like a storyboard and be easy to read. Respondents have suggested support for audio as well as embedded sounds in reviving emotions as well as more meaningful naming conventions while storing the photos. Allowing pictures to represent age of the people involved was also one of the suggestions to put photos in a more historical perspective and hence revive memories. The photos should be able to depict different moods. The ability of adding comments within the photo rather than just naming them with a “.jpeg” extension is also one way images could be stored, which could allow the users to search a picture in reference to the comment they remember from the occasion. We will implement the naming of pictures while they are being downloaded instead of them being stored as some random number with a .jpeg extension and being renamed later by the user.

The response regarding the naming of pictures to allow for better retrieval methods was very encouraging. They ranged from storing pictures in directory structures, allowing for retrieval through dates, business trips, holidays, family and friends etc. Convergence was also a major focus point as all the respondents agreed that they would like a central device to handle the reception, storage and distribution of photos as well as connection to a central media server which can connect to various distribution mediums within the home like TV, Projection Systems, smart boards, Digital photo frames PDA, Phones, etc. The device should also allow for photo editing to accommodate the changes the users want to make to the pictures. It should incorporate the sender/receiver medium built into it. The device should allow for easier and economic means of printing photos. One respondent suggested combining photographs with virtual reality would make photo sharing more fun and enjoyable. Making the pictures more immediate for viewing can support the emotions and intimacy associated with photos.

The only drawback of digital photography has been that it has increased randomisation and duplication of photos, as we tend to take multiple pictures sometimes and store them in random places, hence having multiple copies of a single event, which makes indexing and retrieval of photos harder.

Implications

Novel developments are expected in the methodological approach used, the devices developed and the results of the evaluation of these interfaces will provide insight to how users cope with the technology and the ubiquitous paradigm when sharing photos. What will be required is technology that will create a calm and comforting environment to share pictures within our homes. The research aims at answering some of the questions about people and their relationship with pictures as well as the adoption of ubiquitous technology in the home. The more you can do by intuition the smarter you are and the computer should extend your subconscious [2]. We hope to provide an easy to learn photo sharing solution which can provide an efficient searching, browsing, storing, and annotating of pictures in our homes.

We will look at the social implications of this type of technology, which is characterised by our dependence on technology, control over the information to which everyday objects are linked and the protection of privacy [1] especially if the central server is connected to the Internet and the information is available for others to see. Sharing digital photos on computer networks has been proposed as a new way for people to maintain social relationships [8]. We have discussed this idea and illustrated it with a framework supporting the reception, storage, distribution and emotional implications of digital photographs.

We want to find out what aspects of a particular picture allow the user to conjure up personal thoughts and how they can affectively attach those thoughts to the pictures. Even though there are a few photo sharing sites on the Internet, they do not allow the person at the other end of the network to see what you are thinking. Our photo-sharing prototype will allow people to experience the emotional attachment with pictures, which is so important in maintaining social relationships. Projects like ConFoto and Flickr [14, 15] have made photo sharing easier through semantic annotation of photos through the web. However they still lack when it comes to attaching emotions to pictures in the form of audio, voice to text, or video representation of the viewer's facial expressions.

Conclusion

Digital photography is growing rapidly, especially with the fall in prices of digital cameras and other accessories like Mobile phones and PDA's coming with ever more powerful digital

cameras built into them. This has forced us to find better ways to organize, manage, browse, view and share libraries of photos. We carried out this survey to measure the attitude of people towards digital photography, photo sharing and how we could design a prototype, which would help them in making this experience more fun and enjoyable. We wanted to know about what people want from photo sharing, what they enjoy, how specific design attributes will make them feel, what will delight them and how through this design process their experience might be enhanced. The research will help in finding the factors, which influence the performance of the user and their interaction with the interface, both positively and negatively. We want to design a system, which would provide a relaxed atmosphere to view the photos in and take the passivity out of photo sharing. We want to provide the users with a photo sharing software where the users can attach emotions to the digital pictures, use personal annotations to store and retrieve pictures from a database, and view them on different viewable platforms.

Our next step in the development process is to use the data collected from this survey and implement some of the features in the prototype. We will look at how we could make people attach emotions to a picture and use this aspect in search and retrieval of pictures from photo albums and find a better way of annotating pictures.

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